

Farm Business Owners and Other Investors in Southern Kaduna's Organizational Performance: Implications for Organizational (Workplace) Counselling

Benedict, Rev. Fr. Dr. Bahago
Samaila Educational Foundations
Department Veritas University
Abuja

Romanus Nduji, Christian Oriaku
Business Administration Department
Veritas University
Abuja

GOTIP, Nehemiah Wokji
Department of Arts and Social
Science Education Veritas University
Abuja

Abstract:- The impact of the Southern Kaduna killings on agricultural company owners and other investors' organizational performance, as well as the implications for organizational (workplace) counselling, were investigated in this study. Two research questions and two hypotheses were generated to lead the investigation. The study employed a descriptive survey research approach. A total of 200 agricultural company owners were included in the study's sample. The sample was chosen using a simple random sampling procedure. Data was gathered using a standardized questionnaire. The questionnaire was validated by two test and measurement professionals. The instrument's reliability was assessed, and it received a Cronbach Alpha coefficient of 0.82. To answer the research questions, the obtained data was analysed using the mean, and the research hypotheses were tested using the t-test at the 0.05 level of significance. The study discovered that forced displacement, as well as extrajudicial killings, had a considerable negative influence on agricultural business owners and other investors' organizational performance. The report suggests that legislation be enacted to control Fulani herders' relationships with investors, businessmen and women, and all other Nigerian citizens, based on the findings.

Among the themes discussed include deaths in Southern Kaduna, forced displacement, extrajudicial killings, organizational counselling, and farm business owners.

I. INTRODUCTION

Businesses are no longer secure in Kaduna State, which is currently engaged in a humanitarian crisis (Garba, 2017). The state's southern part has become a hotbed of lethal violence, the majority of which is conducted by herders against farming towns, stifling economic and business activities. Two broader issues, notably in the North Central region, frame this issue: Fulani herdsman attacks on farming villages and reprisal. In the past, Plateau State (especially the Barkin Ladi area) was the epicentre, followed by Nasarawa State, and then Benue State. In these areas, entire communities have been displaced, many people have died, and many farmers have been unable to plant or harvest for years. The focus of the violence has switched from Nigeria's central belt to a northern state, aggravating historic tensions in Southern Kaduna.

Fulani pastoralists appear to outnumber any other animal husbandry group in Nigeria. They are the most prosperous. Nigerians can now buy cattle meat at a reasonable price. For the inhabitants, animal meat is an important source of protein. As a result, they contribute significantly to Nigeria's economy. According to Abbas (2020), the Fulani "indisputably comprise a substantial component of the Nigerian economy," as they are the country's primary cattle breeders and meat producers, as well as the most widely available and cheapest source of animal protein. Over 90% of the country's cattle is owned by the Fulani, who account for one-third of agricultural GDP and 3.2 percent of total GDP.

Herdsman's regular attacks on Nigerian farmers, businesspeople, entrepreneurs, and residents, however, are highly alarming these days. Herdsman were previously known to cause chaos in certain Nigerian towns, according to Adetula (2019), but the rate at which they commit these crimes has escalated enormously. This puts Kaduna State's companies, peace, security, and unity in jeopardy. This negative outlook obscures their substantial economic contribution to the country's gross domestic product (GDP) (Garba, 2000).

Militants from the Fulani ethnic group are thought to have killed at least 1229 people in Nigeria in 2014, according to the latest Global Terrorism Index, which rated African nations as the world's third most terrified countries.

Fulani militants and the terror group Boko Haram killed more than 7000 people in Nigeria in 2014. When it comes to terrorism in Nigeria, Boko Haram dominates the headlines, yet little is known about Fulani herdsmen assaults and kidnappings.

II. THE STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Herdsmen attacks against Nigerian farmers, merchants, entrepreneurs, and civilians in Kaduna state's north-central region are particularly alarming. Conflicts in Southern Kaduna, primarily between indigenous farmers and so-called settler pastoralists, have escalated alarmingly since 2015, with daily reports of killings and the destruction of businesses and buildings worth billions of Naira.

In December 2016, the Catholic diocese of Kafanchan stated that settler pastoralists killed 808 individuals in 53 villages and torched 1,422 dwellings across the local government areas (LGAs) of Kaura, Sanga, Jama'a, and Kauru over the course of a year. Farm produce worth a total of N5.5 billion was also damaged. Kaduna State Governor Nasir El Rufai admitted the intruders were Fulani herdsmen, saying the state administration needed to soothe and pay them to end the killings. In revenge for their rustled cows, as retaliation for the slaughter of any of their members, or to ensure access to grass for their cows, these so-called herdsmen have gone mad, murdering and destroying businesses and villages during the previous four years. Fulani gunmen murder vulnerable and innocent women, children, the elderly, and the sick late at night or early in the morning when the men have gone to their farms. In Southern Kaduna, farming and most other enterprises are no longer safe to run. Gender-based assassinations, honour-based assassinations, forced displacement, extrajudicial assassinations, and other crimes have become the norm, according to Emeka et al (2017). Although studies have been undertaken on the impact of southern Kaduna killings on many sectors, none has particularly focused on the impact of such killings on agricultural business owners' performance. As a result of the aforementioned, the researcher wants to know how the southern Kaduna killings have affected farm business owners, other enterprises, and the threat to food security.

III. EXAMINING THE LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

A. Nigeria's Forefathers: Fulani Herders

In January 2013, Fulani herders raided villages in Nasarawa State, killing ten people and displacing nearly 5000 others. According to Eniola, roughly 33 persons were slain in a new attack in different villages in Nasarawa State in November 2014. Armed Fulani herders committed fresh attacks in 2016. According to Duru, Fulani herders assaulted Agatu Local Government Area in Benue State in February 2016, driving roughly 7000 people from six communities (2016). The people witnessed no military or security presence despite the herdsmen's intense firing. More than 200 individuals were murdered, and a large number of dwellings were destroyed. In April 2016, armed herders assaulted Agatu once more. The fresh violence claimed the

lives of 30 persons, according to the Benue State Emergency Management Agency.

On April 25, 2016, Fulani herdsmen assaulted Ukpabi Nimbo in the Uzo-Uwani Local Government Area, murdering around 40 people, according to Mamah et al. (2016). Survivors were able to make their way to nearby communities. Fulani herdsmen assaulted the Umuchigbo hamlet in Enugu State's Enugu East Local Government Area two days after the Ukpabi Nimbo massacre. Arms-wielding herdsmen's violent exploits are alarming. They've left their imprint on practically every corner of the United States. In recent outings, they have been particularly severe on the villages.

Fulani ethnic militants killed at least 1229 people in Nigeria in 2014, according to the latest Global Terrorism Index, making Africa the world's third most terrorized country. Fulani militants and the terror group Boko Haram killed more than 7000 people in Nigeria in 2014. When it comes to terrorism in Nigeria, Boko Haram dominates the headlines, yet little is known about Fulani herdsmen assaults and kidnappings.

B. Concept of Forced Displacement

The concept of forced displacement has been around for a long time. According to Idegu (2018), forced displacement is the forcible or compelled removal of a person or individuals from their home or home region. Natural catastrophes, violence, ethnic cleansing, persecution of individuals or groups, droughts, civil wars, deportation, and population transfer are all potential causes for this movement. According to Bello, forced relocation has garnered attention in international discussions and policymaking since the European migrant crisis (2018). As a result, the consequences of forced migration in non-European countries have gained increased attention. Various international, regional, and local organizations are creating and implementing solutions in both the sending and receiving regions to prevent and minimize the harmful consequences of forced migration. In addition, certain coordinated efforts are conducted to acquire evidence in order to pursue punishment of individuals guilty for creating forced migratory events caused by humans. Over 60 million people have been forcefully relocated since the turn of the century, the majority of them are from the Global South.

C. Concept of Extrajudicial Killing

The word "extrajudicial execution" refers to the act of killing someone without their consent.

Extrajudicial killings have been somewhat widespread since the conclusion of World War II, but they are not criminalized to the same extent as torture, despite their similar history and frequency. They're tied to the fate of people whose governments have "disappeared" them. For example, in Argentina, liberals and communists who resisted the reigning military junta were executed or simply "disappeared," and during Operation Condor from the 1970s to the 1990s, Chile and other nations with military government participated in systematic extrajudicial killings. Tolu et al. (2019) defines "extrajudicial killing" as "a deliberate killing not authorized by a previous judgment

pronounced by a regularly constituted court providing all the judicial guarantees recognized as essential by civilized peoples," but this term excludes any killing carried out lawfully under the authority of a foreign nation under international law. According to Duru (2016), extrajudicial executions were once uncommon but are now occurring in a variety of countries. One of the most well documented recent examples of extrajudicial killing is now going place in the Philippines. Human Rights Watch claims that seven extrajudicial killings and three forced disappearances have happened recently, despite the current president's campaign to end violence. Hundreds of persons, the majority of whom are political activists and journalists, have gone missing or been slain. According to at least one human rights lawyer, the killings are prevalent enough to constitute a crime against humanity.

Extrajudicial killing, also known as political assassination, is the unlawful killing of prominent political, trade union, dissident, and/or social figures by the state government, state authorities such as the armed forces and police (as in Liberia under Charles G. Taylor), or criminal organizations such as the Italian Mafia⁵, according to Mkutu(2016). Extrajudicial executions are sometimes known as 'targeted killing,' which refers to the practice of killing someone without recourse to the law.

According to Gleick (2019), extrajudicial executions are "any and all homicides committed by State security or similar forces (death squads, and justiceirosor'justice makers' with official involvement, support, or acquiescence) where the victim is denied the right to a legal defense, is executed before being sentenced, or after a trial in which fundamental guarantees are violated" (Ibenwa&Uroko, 2017).

D. Concept of Torture

"Any act in which severe pain or suffering, whether physical or mental, is intentionally inflicted on a person for the purpose of obtaining information or a confession from him or a third person, punishing him or a third person for an act he or a third person has committed or is suspected of having committed, intimidating or coercing him or a third person, or for any reason based on discrimination of any kind, when such pain or It excites him or a third person," Tol

"Torture" is defined by Okoli and Atelhe (2020) as "any act directed against an individual in the offender's custody or physical control by which severe pain or suffering (other than pain or suffering arising only from or inherent in, or incidental to, lawful sanctions), whether physical or mental, is intentionally inflicted on that individual for such purposes as obtaining information or a confession from that individual or a third person, punishing that individual."

E. Gender-Based Violence (GBV)

Female-on-Female Violence is a serious problem.

The World Health Organization (WHO) defines gender-based violence as violence directed against a woman because she is a woman or that disproportionately affects women in its General Recommendation. This includes acts of physical, mental, or sexual harm or suffering, as well as threats of such acts, coercion, and other deprivations of liberty.

Gender-based violence (GBV) is defined as violence directed at a person based on his or her biological sex or gender identity, according to Okeke and Ibenwa (2017). This isn't to say that all acts of violence against women are based on gender, or that all victims of gender-based violence are women. Men may be harassed, beaten, or killed because they don't conform to society's accepted definitions of masculinity.

F. Concept of Organizational (Workplace) Counselling

According to Capital Choice Counselling (2022), workplace (organizational) counselling is a cost-effective and proactive people management strategy that helps employees better manage stress, personal issues, and work-related issues by providing a safe place for them to talk about issues that bother them and find healthy and productive ways to solve them.

G. There is a need for (workplace) counselling in every organization.

According to Capital Choice Counselling (2022), some of the advantages of organizational counselling in any specific organization or workplace include:

- Among other things, a workplace counsellor can act as a thinking companion, revealing mirror, and pacesetter.
- With the assistance of a counsellor, employees' core capabilities can be maximized.
- A counsellor can help create a culture that encourages organizational learning and development to be more synergistic.
- Employees can work with a counsellor to improve their self-awareness of their thinking patterns and behavioural tendencies, allowing them to be more effective as individuals and, as a result, at work.
- People can learn to manage themselves with the guidance of a counsellor, which will help them grow as persons.

H. The advantages of organizational (workplace) counselling

Some of the advantages of organizational counselling are as follows:

- Reduce costs associated with turnover, burnout, absenteeism, and accident-related incapacity.
- Productivity has increased because of improved employee performance.
- In dealing with behavioural challenges that occur as a result of organizational changes, a counsellor might work as a business partner.

Our educational system, however, does not adequately prepare us for everyday life.

IV. EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Nwokeibe (2015) conducted research on the economic impact of religious killings in Nigeria, with a focus on the Benue crisis, and discovered that the country has suffered greatly as a result of religious strife, and that authorities should take a direct approach to the problem in order to revitalize the economy.

Abdul (2018) conducted research in Borno State on the impact of forced displacement on organizational performance, using questionnaires to collect data from 330 people on the payroll and regression analysis to test hypotheses. Forced displacement, he discovered, had a significant negative impact on the State's organizational performance.

Igweka (2015) researched the influence of honour-based killing on Union Bank PLC's performance in Yobe State, employing 68 junior employees and chi-square analysis to test hypotheses. According to his findings, honour-based killing has a significant negative impact on Union Bank PLC's performance.

Isah (2019) investigated the impact of the Jos killings on the state's SMEs, choosing 54 of them. Data was gathered through questionnaires and oral interviews, and the hypotheses were tested using ANOVA analysis. Finally, he discovered that extrajudicial killings had a significant negative impact on the state's SMEs.

V. WHAT'S CAUSING THE KILLINGS IN SOUTHERN KADUNA?

Many of the conflicts in Nigeria between farmers and Fulani herdsmen are thought to be caused by several factors, which are listed below.

To begin, unauthorized encroachment into farmlands has recently resulted in serious conflicts between farmers and herders because of the damage they cause to crops and fallow lands left to replenish nutrients after long periods of use, according to Idegü (2018). According to Idegü (2018), herdsmen's cows frequently stray into farmers' farmlands without permission, destroying crop nurseries or fully grown crops that the farmers hope to harvest and sell soon.

Second, Fulani herders buy land in their own names while claiming to the people that it is for one of their enterprises; nevertheless, when the landowners discover the land being utilized by herdsmen for cattle business against their will, they realize they have been tricked by the herdsmen, resulting in violence (Garba, 2003).

Third, climate change has been tipped as the most important single factor in causing migration and population displacement, according to Gleick (2019). People displaced by shoreline erosion, coastal flooding, and agricultural disruption will be affected, according to Gleick (2019).

Fourth, one of the factors fuelling herdsmen's activities in Nigeria today is the government's lack of political will to arrest and punish offenders adequately. What happened in Nimbo, Uzo-Uwani Local Government Area, and Enugu

town in 2016, all in Enugu State, is a case in point: Fulani herdsmen attacked farmers in Nimbo, killing over 50 people and destroying property worth thousands of naira, due to a misunderstanding over grazing fields.

Fifth, the government's inability to respond promptly to distress calls and early warning signals is a cause of contention, since it has made it impossible to avoid catastrophes that could have been avoided if the government had responded appropriately to distress calls and attentions.

VI. NEGATIVE EFFECTS OF FULANI KILLINGS ON ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF SOUTHERN KADUNA AND NIGERIA

- **Economic impact:** It is evident that Fulani herdsmen's attacks on farmers have resulted in a significant economic loss in not only Southern Kaduna, but Nigeria as a whole, as detailed lower down this page. We know that whenever farmers are attacked, they flee their farms and find it difficult to return for fear of being attacked again, which can last for a long time, preventing sowing and reaping.

This unquestionably creates a false scarcity of goods and services. According to Ibenwa (2018), the Fulani's frequent attacks on farmers have resulted in inflation and devaluation of the naira.

- **Inflation and naira depreciation:** Simply put, inflation is an increase in the price of goods and services over time, defined by Anyanwuocha (2020) as a persistent rise in the general price level. As previously stated, artificial scarcity created by herdsmen attacks on citizens leads to inflation, which in turn leads to naira depreciation. Curfews limit people's movements, resulting in lower output per capita and a significant reduction in daily output of goods and services, as people can no longer freely travel to their farms, stores, and business centers. Ibenwa (2018) backed up this claim by claiming that the check reduced people's overall output.

The Fulani herdsmen's constant attacks discourage foreign investment by scaring away foreigners who have come to Nigeria to do business. During the attacks, people's lives and property are lost, as well as public companies, film production houses, and industries; foreigners who witness such events become discouraged and close their businesses, returning to their home countries.

When there is a serious attack on citizens, houses are burned down and people are made homeless; as a result, some of the less fortunate are unable to find a home and are housed as IDPs in public buildings. According to Okoli and Ateihe (2020), war creates refugees, and large numbers of people are displaced, referred to as IDPs. People have been displaced from their homes due to arson by Fulani herdsmen, and they are camped out in public buildings.

Because businesses, films, and industries are destroyed during such crises, it takes time for business owners to rebuild their damaged business centers; their

employees are unemployed for a long time, contributing to the growing number of unemployed youths on our streets.) in their interactions with the researcher stated that this was true of any war involving weapons.

• **Effects on education:** These activities lead to the closure of primary and secondary schools, as well as post-secondary institutions; when schools close, the school calendar is adjusted, allowing students to study for longer periods of time. As of now, many schools in most of the affected communities have been closed for the past two years at a stretch, according to one of the victims of the killings in Southern Kaduna.

• **Change in population size:** People who live in areas where Fulani herdsmen attacks are common relocate to areas where they are less likely to be attacked, as happened in southern Kaduna between the middle of 2016 and the beginning of 2017, according to Garba (2017). As a result, the population of Kafanchan residents has decreased while the population of the place they are relocating to has increased.

• **Senseless loss of life and property:** It is well known that when herders attack, tens, hundreds, or thousands of people are killed, and property worth hundreds of thousands of naira is destroyed.

VII. THE STUDY'S OBJECTIVES

The study's major purpose is to see how the killings in southern Kaduna have affected farmers and other businesses in the area.

The precise objectives are as follows:

• To look into the impact of extrajudicial murders on agricultural business owners and other enterprises in Southern Kaduna's organizational performance.

• To determine the impact of forced displacement on farmers and other enterprises in Southern Kaduna.

A. Research-related questions

Two research questions led the investigation.

What impact do extrajudicial executions have on the organizational performance of agricultural business owners and other enterprises in Southern Kaduna?

What is the organizational performance impact of forced migration on agricultural company owners and other firms in Southern Kaduna?

B. Hypotheses for investigation

Two research theories led this investigation.

Extrajudicial executions in Southern Kaduna have had no discernible impact on the organizational performance of farmers and other companies.

Forced displacement has had no substantial impact on the organizational performance of agricultural business owners and other enterprises in Southern Kaduna.

VIII. METHODOLOGY

A survey was given to a sample of farm business owners and other businesses in Southern Kaduna to learn about their thoughts and feelings about Fulani killings, as well as the impact of Fulani killings on their businesses and organizational performance. A total of 200 respondents were chosen from among the owners and investors of farm businesses in Southern Kaduna.

Research Question 1: What is the impact of extrajudicial killings on farm business owners and other businesses in their organizational performances in Southern Kaduna.

IX. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

S/N	Impact of Extrajudicial Killings	Level of Agreement				Mean	Decision
		SA	A	D	SD		
1	The activities of the Fulani herdsmen against farm business owners and other investors have resulted in a huge economic set back in Southern Kaduna	72	55	31	42	2.79	Agreed
2	The activities of Fulani herdsmen have hindered the sowing of seeds and harvesting of food stuff by the business owners	66	71	43	20	2.92	Agreed
3	The Fulani herdsmen frequent attacks on farm business owners and investors create artificial scarcity of goods and services	78	64	39	19	3.01	Agreed
4	The creation of artificial scarcity of goods and services has led to the high inflation in the writing	81	64	41	14	3.06	Agreed
5	The creation of artificial scarcity of goods and services due to Fulani herdsmen killings also brought about devaluation of our naira	70	59	38	33	2.83	Agreed
6	As a result of frequent attack on farm business owners, the traders out of fear refuse to carry food items to the market thereby creating man-made scarcity	68	64	35	33	2.84	Agreed
7	The constant attacks by the herdsmen brought about decrease in output per capita	69	71	42	18	2.96	Agreed
8	The attacks have seriously affected people's movement	64	59	34	43	2.72	Agreed

9	due to insecurity Farm business owners and investors have abandoned their farm industries for safety of their lives first	58	78	44	20	2.87	Agreed
10	Constant attacks have discouraged foreign investment in many large farms business in Southern Kaduna	84	61	30	25	3.02	Agreed
Sectional Mean						2.90	Agreed

Table 1: Mean analysis showing impact of extrajudicial killings on farm business owners and other businesses in their organizational performances in Southern Kaduna

Scale Mean 2.50

From Table 1, it could be observed that the mean values of 2.79, 2.92, 3.01, 3.06, 2.83, 2.84, 2.96, 2.72, 2.87 and 3.02 respectively were in agreement with items 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10. The sectional mean of 2.90 indicated that all the respondents agreed that the activities of the Fulani herdsmen against farm business owners and other investors have resulted in a huge economic setback, hindered the sowing of seeds and harvesting of food stuff by the business owners, the Fulani herdsmen frequent attacks on farm business owners and investors create artificial scarcity of goods and services, the creation of artificial scarcity of goods and services due to Fulani killings has led to the high inflation in the writing, brought about devaluation of our naira, the traders refuse to carry food

items to the market thereby creating man-made scarcity, the constant attacks by the herdsmen brought about decrease in output per capita, affected people’s movement due to insecurity, made farm business owners and investors to abandon their farm industries for safety of their lives first and constant attacks have discouraged foreign investment in many large farms business in Southern Kaduna. Thus, extrajudicial killings had a great impact on farm business owners and other businesses in their organizational performances in Southern Kaduna.

Research Question 2: What is the impact of forced displacement on farm business owners and other businesses in their organizational performances in Southern Kaduna.

S/N	Impact of Forced Displacement	Level of Agreement				Mean	Decision
		SA	A	D	SD		
11	The constant herdsmen attacks have created many refugees and Internally Displaced Persons camps in Southern Kaduna	62	58	32	48	2.67	Agreed
12	It has led to an increase in unemployment as large farms industries are closed up for security reasons	68	72	39	21	2.94	Agreed
13	These are more refugee camps in Southern Kaduna today than ever before in the history of Nigeria	66	69	29	36	2.83	Agreed
14	People are displaced from their houses and villages due to arson by the Fulani herdsmen	61	73	33	33	2.81	Agreed
15	Farm business owners have been rendered jobless as they are afraid to go back to their farms anymore	70	61	34	35	2.83	Agreed
16	Institutions of learning have been closed down for some times and this affects students’ study duration	68	72	30	30	2.89	Agreed
17	Some students have been rendered orphans by the killings of the herdsmen	58	70	43	29	2.79	Agreed
18	The population size of most communities is shrinking as people move out of one place to other places, they feel a bit more secure	65	75	28	32	2.87	Agreed
19	Thousands of lives have been destroyed by the Fulani herdsmen killings	81	65	28	26	3.01	Agreed
20	Properties including food items with billions of naira have been destroyed by the herdsmen attackers	71	62	33	34	2.85	Agreed
Sectional Mean						2.85	Agreed

Table 2: Mean analysis showing impact of forced displacement on farm business owners and other businesses in their organizational performances in Southern Kaduna

Scale Mean 2.50

From Table 2, it could be observed that the mean values of 2.67, 2.94, 2.83, 2.81, 2.83, 2.89, 2.79, 2.87, 3.01 and 2.85 respectively were in agreement with items 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19 and 20. The sectional mean of 2.85 indicated that all the respondents agreed that the constant herdsmen attacks have created many refugees and Internally Displaced Persons camps in Southern Kaduna, led to an

increase in unemployment as large farms industries are closed up for security reasons, led to more refugee camps in Southern Kaduna today than ever before in the history of Nigeria, people are displaced from their houses and villages due to arson by the Fulani herdsmen, farm business owners have been rendered jobless as they are afraid to go back to their farms anymore, institutions of learning have been

closed down for some times and this affects students’ study duration, some students have been rendered orphans by the killings of the herdsmen, the population size of most communities is shrinking as people move out of one place to other places they feel a bit more secure, thousands of lives have been destroyed by the Fulani herdsmen killings and

properties including food items with billions of naira have been destroyed by the herdsmen attackers. Thus, forced displacement had a great impact on farm business owners and other businesses in their organizational performances in Southern Kaduna.

X. RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

The null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H₀₁: Extrajudicial killings have no significant impact on farm business owners and other businesses in their organizational performances in Southern Kaduna

Variables	N	Mean	Std. deviation	Df	t-cal	t-tab	Sig (P-cal)	Remarks
Extrajudicial Killings	200	9.35	1.451	398	7.543	1.649	0.000	Reject Ho ₁
Business Owners	200	7.47	1.323					

Table 3: t-test analysis showing impact of extrajudicial killings on farm business owners and other businesses in their organizational performances in Southern Kaduna

Significant at df=398; P<0.05, t-cal > t-tab

Table 3 showed t-test analysis of impact of extrajudicial killings on farm business owners and other businesses in their organizational performances in Southern Kaduna. The t-cal value of 7.548 was found to be greater than the t-tab value of 1.651 given 398 degrees of freedom at 0.05 level of significance. The t-cal value was significant since it was greater than t-tab value, the null hypothesis was rejected. Also, P-cal was less than the P-set. It implied that extrajudicial

killings had a significant impact on farm business owners and other businesses in their organizational performances in Southern Kaduna. Therefore, extrajudicial killings affected their business performances negatively.

H₀₂: Forced displacement has no significant impact on farm business owners and other businesses in their organizational performances in Southern Kaduna.

Variables	N	Mean	Std. deviation	Df	t-cal	t-tab	Sig (P-cal)	Remarks
Forced displacement	200	7.35	1.352	398	9.548	1.649	0.000	Reject Ho ₂
Business Owners	200	4.49	1.224					

Table 4: t-test analysis showing impact of forced displacement on farm business owners and other businesses in their organizational performances in Southern Kaduna

Significant at df=398; P<0.05, t-cal > t-tab

Table 3 showed t-test analysis of impact of forced displacement on farm business owners and other businesses in their organizational performances in Southern Kaduna. The t-cal value of 9.548 was found to be greater than the t-tab value of 1.649 given 398 degrees of freedom at 0.05 level of significance. The t-cal value was significant since it was greater than t-tab value, the null hypothesis was rejected. Also, P-cal was less than the P-set. It implied that forced displacement had a significant impact on farm business owners and other businesses in their organizational performances in Southern Kaduna. Therefore, forced displacement affected their business performances negatively.

XI. DISCUSSION

In hypothesis one, it could be observed that extrajudicial killings had a significant impact on farm business owners and other businesses in their organizational performances in Southern Kaduna. Therefore, extrajudicial killings affected their business performances negatively. This agreed with Isah (2019) who investigated the impact of the Jos extrajudicial killings on the state's SMEs. He discovered that extrajudicial killings had a significant negative impact on the state's SMEs.

In hypothesis two, it could be seen that forced displacement had a significant impact on farm business owners and other businesses in their organizational performances in Southern Kaduna. Therefore, forced displacement affected their business performances

negatively. This corroborated with Abdul (2018), who conducted research in Borno State on the impact of forced displacement on organizational performance of businesses in Borno state. Forced displacement, he discovered had a significant negative impact on the State's businesses organizational performance.

XII. CONCLUSION

The findings of this research have shown that extrajudicial killings, forced displacement and others impacted negatively on Farm Business Owners and Other Investors in Southern Kaduna's Organizational Performance. Therefore, organizational (workplace) counselling is strongly needed to help farm business owners and other investors in their psychological predicament.

XIII. RECOMMENDATIONS

From the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made

- Government to make available organizational (workplace) counselling for all farm owners and other investors in southern kaduna who victims of extrajudicial killings are and forced displacement as it affects their business.
- The study suggests that adequate legislation with severe penalties be enacted to prevent extrajudicial killings and forced displacement in the communities.
- That government should enact legislation that will control Fulani herders' relationships with investors and businessmen in all communities.

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APPENDIX

Impact of Southern Kaduna Killings on Business Owners’ Questionnaire (ISKKBOQ)

S/N	Item	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1	The activities of the Fulani herdsmen against farm business owners and other investors have resulted in a huge economic set back Southern Kaduna				
2	The activities of Fulani herdsmen have hindered the sowing of seeds and harvesting of food stuff by the business owners				
3	The Fulani herdsmen frequent attacks on farm business owners and investors creates artificial scarcity of goods and services				
4	The creation of artificial scarcity of goods and services has lead to the high inflation in the writing now				
5	The creation artificial scarcity of goods and services due to Fulani herdsmen attacks also brought about devaluation of our naira				
6	As a result of frequent attack on farm business owners, the traders out of fear refuse to carry food items to the market thereby creating man made scarcity				
7	The constant attacks by the herdsmen brought about decrease in output per capita				
8	The attacks has seriously affected people’s movement due to insecurity				
9	Farm business owners and investors have abandoned their farm industries for safety of their lives first.				
10	Constant attacks have discouraged foreign investment in many large farms business in Southern Kaduna.				
11	The constant herdsmen attacks has created many refugees and Internally Displaced Persons camps in Southern Kaduna				
12	It has led to increased unemployment as larg farms industries are closed up for security reasons.				
13	These are more refugee camps in Southern Kaduna today more than ever before in the history of Nigeria				
14	People are displaced from their houses and villages due to arson by the Fulani herdsmen.				
15	In Southern Kaduna, farm business owners have been rendered jobless as they are afraid to go back to their farms anymore.				
16	Institutions of learning have been closed down for some times and this affects students study duration.				
17	Some students have been rendered orphans by the killings of the herdsmen in Southern Kaduna				
18	The population size of most communities is shrinking as people move out of one place to other places they feel a bit more secure				
19	Thousands of lives have been destroyed by the Fulani herdsmen				
20	Properties including food items with billions of naira have been destroyed by these herdsmen attackers.				